

Deliverable D-JRP26 WP1.1

Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: RIVM, PIWET

Contributing partners: SCIENSANO, SSI,
ANSES, UCM-VISAVET, Pasteur,

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	JRP26 WP1.1: Detailed work plan																					
Project Acronym	ADONIS																					
Author	Eelco Franz																					
Other contributors	Dariusz Wasyl , Roan Pijnacker, Julio Alvarez, Marianne Chemaly, Nina van Goethem, Eva Litrup, Maria Pardos de la Gandara, Lapo Mughini Gras																					
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):																					
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>international</td> <td>stakeholder(s):</td> </tr> </table> <p>.....</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>		Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>		National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>			EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>		Other	international	stakeholder(s):
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DETAILED WORK PLAN “ ADONIS”

Project summary

Salmonellosis remains the second most common zoonosis in humans in the EU despite a significantly long-term decreasing trend in human cases since 2008. In recent years this decreasing trend has levelled off. In laying hens, the prevalence of positive flocks for the target serovars, and especially for *S. Enteritidis*, has also increased after a long period of documented reduction. Several hypotheses have been made, including more complete reporting and improvements in the surveillance of human salmonellosis, premature relaxation of *Salmonella* control measures at primary production, possible deficiencies in the enforcement of existing control measures and sensitivity of statutory sampling programmes, and changed/increased exposure patterns. The ADONIS project will identify determinants underlying the stagnation/reversal of the decreasing trend in *Salmonella* Enteritidis incidence in humans and poultry in the EU. We will apply a cross-sectorial approach in which we investigate possible explanatory factors at the levels of primary production, epidemiology/exposure, and the pathogen itself. This will all be done over the period that spans the observed turning stagnation point. At the primary production level, the project will evaluate possible changes in flock management and possible insufficiencies in control measures implemented to date in poultry farms related to the implementation of vaccination programmes as well as the application of strict farm hygiene controls and sensitivity of the statutory sampling implemented in commercial flocks. At the public health level, this project will evaluate national surveillance systems for *S. Enteritidis* in humans, assess changes over time regarding epidemiological characteristics, and calculate the total reservoir output exposure loads. At the pathogen level, we will assess whether the recent plateau in salmonellosis incidence in Europe could be related to the genetic variation of the *Salmonella* bacterium, primarily *S. Enteritidis*, such as the emergence or clonal expansion of specific bacterial strains with increased fitness in the form of e.g. increased bacterial division, increased virulence or antibiotic resistance. Finally, the data and information gathered will be ranked and prioritized by a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) modelling

1. Detailed workplans

During the kickoff meeting (Jan 15/16 2020) the ADONIS project team worked, under the lead of the WP leaders, on a more detailed workplan. This was done in the form of X-matrices per WP where goals, tasks and actions to be taken are connected. These X-matrices form the basis of the work to be conducted and the related distribution of responsibilities over partners. I also provides a tool for planning and progress monitoring (result oriented steering).

1.1. Detailed Workplan WP1

●	●	4	D-JRP26 WP1.4 Final report and dissemination (M54)	●						●	0	
●	●	3	D-JRP26 WP1.3 Y4 report (M51)				●			●	0	
●		2	D-JRP26 WP1.2 Y3 report (M39)			●				●	0	
	●	1	D-JRP26 WP1.1 detailed workplan / agreements (M28)	●					●	●	0	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">T2-ST2 Alignment and communication</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">T2_ST1 reporting</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">T1 coordination</div> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 20px;"> <p>Deliverables</p> <p>Tasks</p> <p>Milestones</p> <p>Objectives</p> <p>Overall mission: Efficient and high quality project management</p> </div>				<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">M-JRP26-1 kick-off meeting and production X matrices / agreements (M26)</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">M-JRP26-2 communication plan (and DMP) (M28)</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Prepare draft (9M report) (M36)</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Prepare draft (9M report) (M48)</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Prepare draft (9M report) (M51)</div> <div style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">bi-monthly video conferences with project management team</div> </div>							<div style="background-color: yellow; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Who</div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; margin-top: 10px;"> Eelco / Dariusz WP leaders </div>	
	●	A	Timely and efficient project coordination	★	★							
	●	B	Communication with OHEJP	★						in time		
●		C	Stakeholder relations and communication	★						delayed		
		D		★						overdue		
		E		★						not yet started		
		F										

